

Validity of the Theories of Flory, Kurata, Ptitsyn and Palit on Polymer Molecules in Dilute Solutions as Applied to Some Amylose Derivatives*

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The linear expansion factor, α , for the fractions of sodium amylose xanthate in 1M NaOH and of sodium carboxymethyl amylose in 0.5 M NaCl solution has been determined from the expression due to Orofino and Flory. The validity of the theory of Flory, Kurata and Ptitsyn has been tested in terms of the dependence on molecular weight. Further, an analysis has been made on the Palit's equation in terms of dependence of intrinsic viscosity on molecular weight. It has been observed that the theories due to Ptitsyn and Palit are in good agreement with experimental results.

Assuming Gaussian distribution of the segments of a randomly coiled polymer, Flory and Fox^{1,2} were the first to propose a relation of the type

$$\alpha^5 - \alpha^3 = CN^{1/2} \quad \dots (1)$$

where C is the temperature-dependent parameter related to thermodynamic interactions between segments and solvent, N is the number of chain segments and α is the linear expansion factor. An extensive study of Flory's equation has shown^{3,4} that the value of C is affected by the type of distribution and thus equation (1) is an approximate one. Especially the value of $\frac{\alpha^5 - \alpha^3}{N^{1/2}}$ is not constant but increases with $N^{5,6}$. Two important modifications of equation (1) are due to Kurata, Stockmayer, Roig⁷ and Ptitsyn⁸. The Kurata-Stockmayer-Roig (K-S-R) theory is based on an ellipsoidal model for the distribution of chain segments in place of the spherically symmetrical distribution assumed by Flory and Fox and they proposed the relation

$$\left(1 - \frac{1}{\alpha^2}\right) \left(\alpha^2 + \frac{1}{3}\right)^{3/2} = C^1 N^{1/2} \quad \dots (2)$$

where C^1 is a constant, the value of which depends on the effective bond length, and β , the binary cluster integral of each chain element. The expression of Kurata, Stockmayer and Roig seems to give a better agreement with experimental data. The theory proposed by Ptitsyn takes the interaction between chain segments into consideration and leads to an equation differing substantially from that of Flory and Fox. Taking into consideration the non-gaussian distribution functions for α he derived the equation

$$[(4.68\alpha^2 - 3.68)^{3/2} - 1] = C^1 N^{1/2} \quad \dots (3)$$

*Dedicated to Prof. Santi R. Palit on the occasion of his 60th birth anniversary.

The Ptitsyn equation predicts a stronger dependence of α on the number of chain segments than the Flory equation.

A correlation between the intrinsic viscosity and molecular weight of polymers has been deduced by Palit^{9,10} from consideration of Eyring's rate theory and 'hole' theory of liquids and is given by

$$100\rho_0[\eta] = K_1M^{2/3} - \ln M + K_2 \quad \dots (4)$$

where ρ_0 is the density of the polymer at infinite dilution, K_1 and K_2 being constants. This equation has been found to be valid for a number of synthetic polymers as well as for cellulose derivatives and polypeptides¹¹.

The purpose of the present communication is to examine the validity of these equations from light-scattering and viscosity data obtained from two amylose derivatives, *viz.*, sodium amylose xanthate and sodium carboxymethyl amylose in 1M NaOH and 0.5N NaCl solution respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation and fractionation of sodium amylose xanthate and sodium carboxymethyl amylose has been carried out in the usual way¹².

The viscosity measurements were made in a Ubbelohde capillary viscometer at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. Kinetic energy corrections, being negligible, were not undertaken.

Light-scattering measurements were made at 546 nm in a Brice-Phoenix Universal light-scattering photometer, series 1999-10. The refractive index increments were measured at 546 nm in a Brice-Phoenix differential refractometer, calibrated with KCl solution at 30° .

The expansion factor α was calculated by use of the relationship due to Orofino and Flory¹³ in all cases.

Fig. 1. $(\alpha^5 - \alpha^3)$ vs. $\bar{M}_w^{1/2}$ plot according to Flory for
 O sodium amylose xanthate
 ● sodium carboxymethyl amylose,

TABLE I

Application of different dilute solution theories for sodium amylose xanthate and sodium carboxymethyl amylose in their respective solvents

(1) *Flory-Fox Equation*

System	Sample No.	$\bar{M}_w^{\dagger} \times 10^{-3}$	$\alpha^5 - \alpha^3$
Sodium amylose xanthate in 1M NaOH solution	1a	2.823	1.524
	1b	2.500	1.099
	1c	2.398	0.761
	1d	1.871	0.490
	2a	1.449	0.238
	2b	0.938	0.118
	2c	0.825	0.067
	2d	0.748	0.043
Sodium carboxymethyl amylose in 0.5M NaCl solution	1a	2.530	0.761
	1b	2.289	0.736
	1c	1.804	0.357
	1d	1.342	0.209
	2a	1.484	0.243
	2b	1.118	0.177
	2c	0.885	0.118
	2d	0.768	0.069

(2) *Kurata-Stockmayer-Roig theory*

System	Sample No.	$\bar{M}_w^{\dagger} \times 10^{-3}$	$\left(1 - \frac{1}{\alpha^2}\right)\left(\alpha^2 + \frac{1}{3}\right)^{3/2}$
Sodium amylose xanthate in 1M NaOH solution	1a	2.823	1.170
	1b	2.500	0.933
	1c	2.398	0.719
	1d	1.871	0.514
	2a	1.449	0.315
	2b	0.938	0.155
	2c	0.825	0.092
	2d	0.748	0.061
Sodium carboxymethyl amylose in 0.5M NaCl solution	1a	2.530	0.719
	1b	2.289	0.678
	1c	1.804	0.404
	1d	1.342	0.260
	2a	1.484	0.296
	2b	1.118	0.226
	2c	0.885	0.156
	2d	0.768	0.092

(3) *Ptitsyn equation*

System	Sample No.	$\bar{M}_w^{\dagger} \times 10^{-3}$	$(4.68\alpha^2 - 3.68)^{3/2} - 1$
Sodium amylose xanthate in 1M NaOH solution	1a	2.823	7.69
	1b	2.500	5.92
	1c	2.398	4.35
	1d	1.871	2.97
	2a	1.449	1.57
	2b	0.938	0.80
	2c	0.825	0.42
	2d	0.748	0.29
Sodium carboxymethyl amylose in 0.5M NaCl solution	1a	2.530	4.351
	1b	2.289	4.053
	1c	1.804	2.238
	1d	1.342	1.371
	2a	1.484	1.574
	2b	1.118	1.173
	2c	0.885	0.800
	2d	0.768	0.450

The light-scattering and viscometric data obtained by us have been utilised to test the relationships (1) to (4).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity of Flory-Fox theory : The Flory-Fox theory (equation 1) predicts that a plot of $\alpha^5 - \alpha^3$ Vs. $\bar{M}_w^{1/2}$ should give a straight line passing through the origin. Fig. 1 shows the plot of this type for sodium amylose xanthate and sodium carboxymethyl amylose in their respective solvents. In both the cases, the value of $\alpha^5 - \alpha^3$ shows an increase with increase in molecular weight. Although good linearity of $\alpha^5 - \alpha^3$ Vs. $\bar{M}_w^{1/2}$ plot was obtained in the case of sodium carboxymethyl amylose, the straight line instead of passing through the origin, gave an intercept of 0.25×10^6 in the abscissa. With sodium amylose xanthate, the deviation was even wider and the points of the plot $\alpha^5 - \alpha^3$ Vs. $\bar{M}_w^{1/2}$ were very much scattered. This is due to the fact that the Flory theory, as noted by Kurata and Stockmayer⁷, does not rigorously estimate the excluded volume effects of polymers in solution.

Validity of Kurata-Stockmayer-Roig theory : The molecular expansion was also interpreted in terms of Kurata-Stockmayer and Roig theory of excluded volume effect according to which the plots of $\left(1 - \frac{1}{\alpha^2}\right) \left(\alpha^2 + \frac{1}{3}\right)^2$ Vs. $\bar{M}_w^{1/2}$ should be linear and should pass through the origin (equation 2). Such a plot for sodium amylose xanthate and sodium carboxymethyl amylose is shown in fig. 2. In the case of Na-amylose xanthate, the agreement was excellent

Fig. 2. $\left(1 - \frac{1}{\alpha^2}\right) \left(\alpha^2 + \frac{1}{3}\right)^2$ vs. $\bar{M}_w^{1/2}$ plot according to Kurata-Stockmayer-Roig theory for

- O sodium amylose xanthate
- sodium carboxymethyl amylose.

so far as the linearity was concerned but the plot gave an intercept in the abscissa instead of passing through the origin. The approximate linearity of the graph passing through the origin, however, was obtained in the case of sodium carboxymethyl amylose at least in the low molecular weight level. Thus, with the K-S-R theory, although a better agreement with experimental data was reached, complete accord was not obtained.

Validity of Ptitsyn theory : According to Ptitsyn theory, plots of $[(4.68\alpha^2 - 3.68)^{3/2} - 1]$ Vs. $\bar{M}_w^{1/2}$ are expected to give straight lines passing through the origin (equation 3). Such plots for sodium amylose xanthate and sodium carboxymethyl amylose are shown in Fig. 3 and the approximate linearity of the curves passing through the origin were obtained as required theoretically.

Fig. 3. $[(4.68\alpha^2 - 3.68)^{3/2} - 1]$ vs $\bar{M}_w^{1/2}$ plot according to Ptitsyn theory for
 ○ sodium amylose xanthate
 ● sodium carboxymethyl amylose.

Thus, among the above three theories, the one advanced by Ptitsyn is the most successful in explaining the experimentally observed behaviour of the amylose derivatives in dilute solution. Deviations from the predictions by the Flory theory is very much pronounced in both the cases. The inability of the Flory theory may be caused by the inadequacy of

Fig. 4. Palit's plot for
 ○ sodium amylose xanthate
 ● sodium carboxymethyl amylose.

[the model chosen and the assumptions made in the theoretical expression. The adoption of ellipsoidal model by Kurata, Stockmayer and Roig in place of spherical distribution of the chain segments leads to a better approximation to the experimentally observed behaviour. However, Ptitsyn pointed out that the K-S-R relation was derived for a gaussian chain and its use for chains with excluded volume effect means that the latter changed only the linear dimension of the molecule and had no effect on its cross-section. If the isotopic swelling of the polymer chain is taken into account, the K-S-R relation reverts to the Flory-Fox equation. The K-S-R equation, therefore, while containing a physically unjustified assumption, does not represent a significant improvement over the Flory-Fox theory.

Validity of Palit's equation : The plots of $100\rho_0[\eta] + \ln M_w$ vs. $M_w^{2/3}$ for sodium amylose xanthate and sodium carboxymethyl amylose have been found to be linear (Fig. 4) which show an excellent agreement with the relationship proposed by Palit. We have assumed the value of ρ_0 as unity in Palit's equation (Eqn. 4). The values of K_1 and K_2 are shown in Table 2. K_1 values are thought to increase with increase in chain stiffness while K_2 are dependent on the compactness of packing inside the solvent. The values of K_1 of the order of 10^{-2} and that of K_2 very close to our result have also been obtained for some cellulose derivatives, e.g., cellulose acetate in acetone¹⁴ ($K_1 = 32 \times 10^{-2}$ and $K_2 = 10$) and Benzyl cellulose¹⁵ in chloroform ($K_1 = 15.5 \times 10^{-2}$ and $K_2 = -1$). Thus, Palit's equation is applicable for these derivatives in their respective solvents within certain experimental error.

TABLE 2

Application of Palit's equation for sodium amylose xanthate and sodium carboxymethyl amylose in their respective solvents

System	Sample No.	$M_w^{2/3} \times 10^{-4}$	$100\rho_0[\eta] + \ln \bar{M}_w$	$k_1 \times 10^2$	K_2
Sodium amylose xanthate in 1M NaOH solution	1a	3.999	594.90		
	1b	3.393	496.65		
	1c	3.215	432.57		
	1d	2.305	336.08		
	2a	1.640	262.52	1.40	35
	2b	0.918	171.71		
	2c	0.773	140.41		
	2d	0.679	125.24		
Sodium carboxymethyl amylose in 0.5 M NaCl solution	1a	3.446	493.68		
	1b	3.017	425.45		
	1c	2.194	315.00		
	1d	1.480	217.41	1.35	15
	2a	1.690	244.61		
	2b	1.116	178.04		
	2c	0.849	133.57		
	2d	0.703	115.60		

REFERENCES

1. P. J. Flory and T. J. Fox, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 1904.
2. P. J. Flory, Principles of Polymer Chemistry Cornell University Press, Ithaca, N.Y., 1953.
3. M. Fixman, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1955, **23**, 1656.
4. O. B. Ptitsyn, *Vysokomol. Soedin.*, 1959, **1**, 715.
5. W. R. Krigbaum and D. K. Carpenter, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 1166.
6. M. Notely and P. Debye, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1955, **17**, 99.
7. M. Kurata, W. H. Stockmayer and A. Roig, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1960, **33**, 151.
8. O. B. Ptitsyn, *Vysokomol. Soedin.*, 1961, **3**, 1673.
9. S. R. Palit, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1955, **29**, 65.
10. S. R. Palit, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 721.
11. S. R. Palit and D. K. Sarkar, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1967, **61**, 389.
12. P. K. Manna, Dissertation, Calcutta University, 1972 (submitted).
13. T. A. Orofino and P. J. Flory, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1957, **26**, 1067.
14. A. Bartovics and H. Mark, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 1901.
15. S. Basu and H. B. Roy, *J. Sci. Ind. Res., India*, 1952, **11B**, 94.

